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RECONMATIC enters its final year: training, collaboration, and upcoming initiatives

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After nearly four years of research, innovation, and collaboration, RECONMATIC is entering its final phase. Since its launch in July 2022, the team has been working to transform how the construction industry approaches waste management and circularity.

As we move into this last stage, many exciting developments are taking shape: from the release of training materials and digital sustainability tools to the planning of our final RECONMATIC Conference in May 2026, where partners, researchers, and industry professionals will gather to share results, demonstrations, and insights. Make sure to follow our final journey as RECONMATIC turns research into real-world impact!

RECONMATIC in Bilbao: setting the course for the project's final year

This September, RECONMATIC partners met in Bilbao for the project's third Annual Assembly, hosted by **TECNALIA Research & Innovation**. The two-day meeting brought together partners from across Europe and China to review progress, share recent technological developments, and plan the project's final year. The discussions highlighted the strong collaboration within the consortium and the shared commitment to advancing circular construction and demolition waste management.

[Read more and explore the photo gallery 📸](#)

Family photo of the RECONMATIC consortium in Bilbao, Spain, during the Annual Assembly, hosted by TECNALIA.

Are you a trainer looking to integrate circular construction into your teaching?

The next step in circular construction isn't just about new technologies, it's about people. The sector needs professionals who can apply digital tools and innovative design approaches across the entire building life cycle. Bridging this skills gap starts with educators, those who inspire and train the next generation of experts in sustainable construction.

To support them, RECONMATIC is launching an online Educator Training on Circular Construction on 1 December 2025 (13:00–16:00 CET). This interactive session will introduce the **RECONMATIC Online Learning Platform** developed by **Future Needs**, which offers nine free, open-access courses in English and Chinese.

"The economic value of a circular economy is unlocked only when research is effectively translated into widespread, practical application by every architect, engineer, and policymaker across Europe" - **Anna Palaiologk**, Head of Research & Business Development, Future Needs

During the training, participants will:

- Learn directly from the **lecture authors** behind the course materials.
- Explore the **video-based platform**, presentations, and digital tools hands-on.
- Gain **practical guidance** on integrating these materials into their own teaching and training activities.

RECONMATIC Educator Training on Circular Construction

About the EventThe RECONMATIC Educator Training is a specialised online session designed for educators and trainers who plan to integrate...

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#CircularConstructionCluster (CCC)

It's been a busy season for the CCC!

● Towards the end of summer, two members met in Castellón, Spain, where **Instituto Valenciano de la Edificación (IVE)** and the **ITC - Instituto de Tecnología Cerámica** hosted a productive meeting to explore collaborations between the **DeCO2 Horizon Europe Project** and **RECONMATIC** projects, paving the way for stronger synergies and greater impact.

● In September, the cluster **held a member meeting** focused on planning the next joint activities and strengthening cooperation among EU projects.

● And in October, the CCC **was presented at the Sustainable Places** conference by **Ioannis Koutsos** from Future Needs, engaging an EU-wide audience committed to advancing circular construction.

Help shape a circular future in construction

Did you know that the construction industry generates over 10 billion tonnes of waste every year - up to 65% of all landfill content? Reaching net zero waste by 2050 demands a shift toward a circular economy, where materials are reused, repaired, and recycled for as long as possible.

As part of the RECONMATIC project, we've developed the Circularity Assessment Tool (CAT) to understand how circular economy principles are being implemented across Europe, the UK, and China.

By taking part, you'll help us identify current practices, country baselines, and opportunities to boost waste reduction and recovery through automation.

 Take Part in the Circularity Assessment (CAT)

Take Part in the Circularity Assessment (CAT)

The construction industry is currently the largest waste producer in the world, generating more than 10 billion tonnes of construction and demolition...

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From waste to value: how TECNALIA's robotic technologies developed in RECONMATIC are reinventing construction waste sorting

Concrete, ceramics, wood, plasterboard, plastic, and contaminant materials like gypsum or asbestos often end up in a mixed stream, making automated separation particularly challenging. Traditional sorting systems rely on manual labour or simple mechanical processes, which limit efficiency, safety, and material quality in recycling.

To meet the challenge of producing high-purity, high-quality recycled materials, RECONMATIC partner **TECNALIA Research & Innovation** robotics team set out to develop a solution that combines multisensory integration, AI-driven material recognition, and robotic sorting.

Insights from [Dr. Ibon Merino Bermejo, PhD](#) and [Damien Sallé](#)

From Waste to Value: How TECNALIA's Robotic technologies developed in RECONMATIC are reinventing Construction Waste Sorting

From Waste to Value: How TECNALIA's Robotic technologies...

Automation is unlocking a new era for circular construction. and RECONMATIC is leading the way. With the development of intelligent robotic...

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RECONMATIC Open Day returns to China in spring 2026

Following the success of [last year's Open Day in Shaoxing](#), which brought together experts from China, Europe, and the UK to exchange knowledge on automated solutions for circular construction, we're excited to announce that the Chinese RECONMATIC Open Day will take place in Spring 2026 in Beijing, China.

The event will once again provide a platform for researchers, innovators, and industry leaders to connect and advance the sustainable and circular management of construction and demolition waste (CDW).

European and Chinese representatives of the RECONMATIC project at the RECONMATIC Open Day in Shaoxing 2024.

Interested in joining us? Register your interest now to be among the first to receive updates and details as they become available. For more information, please contact our partner [Jia W. LI](#).

RECONMATIC on the international stage

#digitaltwins #hpc #hidalgo2clusteringevent | Georgi...

Coming to the end of this productive week, I reflect on the exceptional three days I had in Stuttgart, organising and participating in the HiDALGO2...

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RECONMATIC at Waste Forum 2025 Symposium in Hustopeče near Brno

RECONMATIC at Waste Forum 2025 Symposium in Hustopeče near Brno Last week, our project coordinator, Jan Valentin, together with Pavel...

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#circularconstructioncluster #sp25 #sustainableplaces2025 |...

Hello from Milan and Sustainable Places Conference 2025! 🏢 🌱 RECONMATIC co-hosted the EU workshop "Ctrl+ Rebuild: Supporting...

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RECONMATIC presents sustainable construction waste management...

On 12 September 2025, RECONMATIC partner Teresa Ros Dosedá from ITC - Instituto de Tecnología Cerámica, presented the results of ou...

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Meet the RECONMATIC team at the upcoming event

📍 **Digital Construction Week** | November 19 - Join us at the Manchester Information Management Stage at 11:00 AM, where our partners **Morgan Sindall Construction**, **The University of Salford** and **BIMBox** will be attending and presenting. Don't miss the opportunity to connect with our team and learn more about how RECONMATIC is driving innovation in circular construction and digital transformation.

🤝 Want to collaborate with RECONMATIC or join our final hybrid conference in Europe in May?

Get in touch with our Dissemination Leader, **Egle Joneliunaite** from Future Needs, to explore potential synergies and help shape the future of circular construction!

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